

Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) Contribution to the Staff Improvement and Research and Publication of Higher Institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria, from 2015 to 2020

Bala Bakwai Kwashabawa, Ph.D

Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, P. M. B. 2346, Sokoto, Nigeria

Nura Mustapha

Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero P. M. B. 1146, Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria

Abstract

This study is on the assessment of the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) contribution to the staff improvement and research and publication of higher institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria from 2015-2020. The study adopted a survey research design to enable the researcher to assess the TETFund contribution for the improvement of research and publication of higher institutions in Kebbi State. The study selected 161 out of 1900 academic staff total of the population and 196 out of the 2323 on non-academic staff of the entire population of the study using the Research Advisors Table (2006) for determining the sample size. The study used a questionnaire as an instrument for collecting data. The method of data analysis was frequency count and percentage. The study found that TETFund contributed to staff improvement through TETFund normal intervention by sponsoring of local and international training to academic staff and sponsoring local seminars and conferences or workshops to academic and non-academic staff of Kebbi State higher institutions and TETFund contributed to the improvement of research and publication through normal intervention by sponsoring of journal publications and researches and book publications of higher institutions in Kebbi State. It is also recommended that TETFund should live up to its expectations in terms of normal intervention on staff improvement that would aid the effective improvement of higher institutions in Kebbi State and that publishers should complement the effort of TETFund in assisting the Kebbi State higher institutions staff in the publication of their books and journals without payment. Such publishers should be encouraged by the State Government by granting them tax relief and other incentives for smooth operations.

Keywords: *Higher Institutions, TETFUND, Kebbi State, Nigeria.*

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Introduction

Education is the most powerful tool for the development of personality and human skills, and is required for any nation to progress. It provides individuals with the necessary direction for their attitudes and behaviours. It is a full-fledged, all-encompassing process that helps people thrive and rapidly grow in this world. There is only one tool that is crucial for managing future challenges and bringing about change in any society, and that tool is education (Bhojaraju et al., 2005). Using education as a tool, the government hopes to produce manpower that will serve in different capacities and contribute positively to the nation's socio-economic and political development. Specifically, the government intends to gear higher institutions towards high-level relevant manpower training, self-reliance, national utility and international understanding (Johnson & Oloruntoba, 2020). In pursuit of these objectives, higher institutions such as Universities, Polytechnics, Colleges of Education and Mono-technics are established in different parts of the country by the government, private organisations and individuals.

Idowu (2020) view higher institutions as the types of schools which a student will be attended after secondary school such as Universities, Polytechnics, Monotechnic Colleges of Education and other Institutions of higher learning offering correspondence courses, diplomas and certificates. Ibrahim (2017) explained that higher institutions are very important in meeting the socio-cultural and developmental needs of a country. The Higher institution provides an opportunity for individuals to develop their potential. It fulfils the needs for high-level manpower in a society. Its objectives include cultural and material development to meet the learning needs and aspirations of individuals through the development of their intellectual abilities and aptitudes throughout their lives. Higher education equips individuals to make the best use of their talents and of the opportunities offered by society for self-fulfilment. The ultimate goal of higher institutions is to produce graduates who will be effective leaders in their chosen professions, valued members of their communities, and responsible citizens of the world. It is the desire to develop higher institution to the required level capable for encouraging sound national integration and development in all aspects of national life that contributed to the emergence of the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) in Nigeria.

Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) is a government intervention agency responsible of providing supplementary supports to all level of public higher institutions with the main aim of using funding to restore all the lost objectives of higher institutions in Nigeria (Jumare & Muhammad, 2019).

The mandate of the Fund as provided in section 7 (1) (a) to (e) of the TETFUND Act, 2011 is to administer and disburse the amount in the fund to Federal and State Higher Educational Institutions, specifically for the provision and maintenance of the physical infrastructure for teaching and learning; instructional material and equipment; research and publication; staff training and development; any other need arise, which is critical and essential for the improvement of quality standards and maintenance of higher educational Institutions would be considered by the Board of Trustees (Ibrahim, 2017).

The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) has been very instrumental in the area of funding higher education in Nigeria since it was established. Public higher institutions have been benefiting in several ways through TETFund. Despite the establishment of TETFund, Nigerian citizens continue to complain regarding poor funding and inadequate infrastructure in high institutions in Nigeria. The study on Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) is very significant in the sense that the fund since its establishment has been contributing immensely to the development of higher institutions in Nigeria. Notwithstanding, few and not many are able to understand and appreciate the contribution of TETFund in the improvement of higher institutions in the Kebbi State. Various studies have been conducted on the improvement of higher institutions in the country without non-examining the role of the TETFund in the staff improvement and research and publication of higher institutions in Kebbi State. In view of the above, the researcher intends to study TETFund contribution to the staff improvement and research and publication of higher institutions in Kebbi State.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian higher educational system began to be depressed in 1980s and beyond due to funding problems. The decay at all levels of education increased, facilities had almost collapsed; teachers' and lecturers' morale were at the lowest due to the low budgetary allocation. Enabling an environment for conducive teaching and learning was absent. This has resulted in poor education outcomes, especially in higher institutions. Government came out with measure to arrest the decay which resulting the establishment Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund). TETFund has been very instrumental in the area of funding higher education in Nigeria since it was established. Public higher institutions have been benefiting in several ways through TETFund. Despite the establishment of TETFund, Nigerian citizens continue to complain about regarding poor funding and inadequate infrastructure in high institutions in Nigeria.

Given the contribution of TETFund for the improvement of higher institutions in Nigeria several studies have examined both theoretical and empirical link to contribution of TETFund to improvement of higher institutions. Some of these studies include among others Abba (2020); Jasper & Aliyu (2021) and Bhojaraju et al (2005). However, these studies concentrated more attention on the training of academic staff and infrastructure development in higher institutions in the North eastern region. While some of the studies concentrate on quality assurance and entrepreneurship education, little attention was given on TETFund contribution for the improvement of higher institutions such a staff improvement and improvement of research and publication. This is one of the gaps created in knowledge. It is the desire to bridge gaps that this study intends to assess the contribution of TETFund to the improvement of staff and research and publication of higher institutions in Kebbi State.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims at achieving the following objectives:

1. To assess the contributions of TETFund to the staff improvement in higher institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020.
2. To assess the contributions of TETFund to the improvement of research and publication in higher institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the contributions of TETFund to staff improvement in higher institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020?
2. What are the contributions of TETFund to the improvement of research and publication in higher institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020?

Literature Review

The higher institutions in Nigeria consist of Universities, Polytechnics, Monotechnics and Colleges of Education and Agricultural Institute. In Nigeria, there are currently 221 approved universities in Nigeria comprising 50 Federal Universities, 60 State Universities and 111 Private Universities (NUC, 2023). Also, Nigeria has a total 159 approved Polytechnics and 152 approved Colleges of Education in Nigeria, making it the largest higher education system on the African Continent.

The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013a) section 5 subsection 80 - 85 specifies that the goals of higher education shall be to: Contribute to national development through high level manpower training; provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interest of Nigerians; provide high-quality career counselling and lifelong learning opportunity that prepare students with knowledge and skills for self-reliance; reduce skills shortages through the production of relevant skilled workers; promote and encourage scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and promote national and international understanding and interaction.

For to become reality, the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) was established by an Act of the National Assembly in June 2011. The Act replaced the Education Tax Fund Act Cap. E4 laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 and Education Tax Fund (Amendment) Act No 17, 2003. The Fund was established to administer and disburse education tax collections to the Federal and State tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria for the rehabilitation, restoration and consolidation of Tertiary Education in Nigeria. It is an intervention organisation established to provide supplementary support to all levels of public tertiary institutions with the primary goal of using funding in conjunction with project management. The main source of income available to the Fund is the two percent education tax paid from the assessable profit of companies registered in Nigeria. The Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS) assesses and collects the tax on behalf of the Fund. The funds are disbursed for the general improvement of education in federal and state tertiary educations specifically for the provision or maintenance of essential physical infrastructure for teaching and learning, institutional material and equipment, research and publications, academic staff training and development and any other need which, in the opinion of the Board of Trustees, is critical and essential for the improvement and maintenance of standards in the higher educational institutions (Ibrahim, 2017).

Specifically, Objectives of the TETFUND are: to continuously improve Education Tax Revenue by ensuring that the tax is collected and made available for Fund intervention programmes; to deliver appropriate and adequate intervention programmes with due regard to the sensitivities of beneficiaries and stakeholders; to promote cutting - edge technologies, ideas and organizational skills in education, and

ensure that projects are forward-looking as well as responding to present needs; to ensure successful completion of intervention projects; to form a viable and enduring partnership between the TETFund and its beneficiaries; to manage Education Tax in a way that is most beneficial to the Nigerian people; and to recruit, retain, train and retrain a highly motivated workforce (Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Tetfund) 2012 – 2016, 2019).

TETFund intervention funds can easily be accessed by guidelines established by the Board of Trustees of the Fund in line with its enabling Act. An institution must be enlisted by approval of the Board of Trustees of TETFund to qualify as a beneficiary of TETFund intervention funds. To be enlisted as a TETFund beneficiary, the following must be fulfilled by prospective institutions: The prospective beneficiary must be a Public Tertiary Institution, that is, federal or state university, polytechnic and college of education; the institution must be recognised by the relevant regulatory body – NUC, NBTE or NCCE as the case may be and evidence of this should be available both with the institution and the regulatory body for citing; the institution must have been established by law via an Act of Parliament or Edict of the State House of Assembly and signed into law by the President or State Governor, as the case may be; Academic activities, that is, student admission, teaching and learning, must have commenced at the institution; The prospective institution shall formally apply to the Fund to be enlisted as a beneficiary of the fund; TETFund shall visit to verify that academic activities have commenced and thereafter recommend to the Board of Trustees for enlistment as a beneficiary; Following approval by the Board of Trustees, the institution shall be enlisted and formally notified.

TETFund as an intervention agency and its scope is limited, in line with its enabling Act, as amended, to provide supplementary support to all public owned tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

TETFUND Normal Interventions/Annual Interventions

This is the type of intervention comprises physical infrastructure, equipment, Library development, academic staff training and development, research, journal publication, conference attendance, manuscript development, ICT support and entrepreneurship centre. The normal intervention is yearly for all beneficiaries' institutions (TETFund, 2014).

Library Development Intervention: Is a type of normal intervention aims to enhance and support academic environment within higher institutions. This intervention typically focuses on improving library infrastructure, resources and services to foster learning, research and knowledge dissemination among students, faculty and researchers (Tetfund, 2015).

Academic Staff Training and Development: This programme of the Fund is also called TETFund Scholarship Programme is a normal intervention line under the Academic Based Intervention Areas aimed at upgrading the quality of teaching staff of public tertiary institutions, through the award of scholarships for masters and doctorate degrees both within Nigeria and universities outside the country. Apart from award of scholarships, this programme also includes Bench-Work sponsorships for those pursuing science based Doctorate Degree Programme in Nigerian Universities to carry out research work in foreign institutions with advanced facilities (Social & Issn, 2021).

Institution Based Research: The IBR was established with the objective of resuscitating research activities in the nation's tertiary institutions in Nigeria; the culture of research over the years has been dwindling in most of the higher Institutions in the country. The outcome of which would be the revival of quality research among lecturers in higher institutions.

Conference Attendance: The conference attendance programme started in 2010 according to the Fund. The main objective of the intervention is to create opportunities for both academic and non-academic staff of public tertiary institutions to interface with their peers at the international and local levels aimed at acquiring new ideas and improve their knowledge in their areas of specialisation (Social & Issn, 2021).

Entrepreneurship Development Intervention: This intervention was introduced aim to cultivate a culture of entrepreneurship, innovation and self-reliance among students of higher institution and the broader community, contributing to economic development, job creation and societal progress.

Research Methodology

The researcher used a survey design method in carryout study. A survey design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analysing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group and how such data will be collected and analysed (Oben, 2021) . The design was considered appropriate for the study because it allow for the collection of data from the sample which will be true representation of the population.

The population of this study comprised all the, academic and non-academic staff of the Kebbi State higher institutions. There are 4 higher institutions in Kebbi State who are TETFund beneficiaries for the past 5 years, with 1900 academic staff and 2323 non-academic staff. The study used a multi stage sampling procedure to determine the sample of the study. The researcher used the Research Advisors (2006) for determining the sample size of academic staff and non-academic staff of higher institutions under study which recommended a sample size of 357 out of a total population of 4223 of academic staff and non-academic staff. A proportionate sampling technique was used to determine the sample size required from each higher institution.

The instrument that was used in this study is a self-designed questionnaire entitled "Improvement of Higher Institutions Questionnaire" (IHIQ) for academic staff and non- academic staff. Questionnaires offer the advantage of being easy and cost effective to administer to a large population (Taherdoost, 2021). The instrument comprised two Parts I and II. Part I contained 4 items designed to collect demographic data of the respondents such as gender, educational qualification, category of staff and type of higher institutions, while part II was broken into two sections namely sections A-B covering the two research questions and each section has 5 items. The questionnaire has a total of ten (10) items. All questions are positive closed ended questions where respondents are restricted to pick one response on opinions proposed from four Likert type scale responses namely: Strongly Agree (SA) 4 points, Agree (A) 3 points, Disagree (D) 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1 point.

The instrument was face validated by three (3) experts' scrutiny in the field of Test and Measurement, Research and Statistics and Educational Management respectively. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument a pilot study was conducted using forty (40) respondent drawn from academic staff and non-academic staff from Sokoto State

University, Sokoto Nigeria who were are not part of the sample of the study. The questionnaire was administered to them two times within the interval of three weeks to establish the stability other times. The results were compared using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Coefficient (PPMC) where an index of 0.76 was obtained. The simple statistical method was used which involve tables, percentages and frequency count to analyses data. Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. From the 357 questionnaires administered, 350 were filled and returned by the respondents.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This section presented the analysis of responses from the questionnaires administered using descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency counts and tables for easy and better understanding. A total of 357 questionnaires were distributed but only a total of 350 were returned which were used for the calculations.

Research Question One

RQ1: What are the contributions of TETFund to staff improvement in higher institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020?

This research question was answered and presented in Table 2 (Appendix 1).

In Table 2 (Appendix 1) item 1 showed that 75% of the respondents involves in the study strongly agreed with the view that, their institution benefited from staff development through TETFUND normal intervention from 2015-2020, 25% of them agreed while 0% disagreed and 1% of them strongly disagreed with the view. Item 2 indicated that 55% of the respondents strongly agree that TETFund sponsors local and international training to academic staff in their institutions, 43% of them agreed while 8% disagreed and 0% strongly disagreed with the view. Item 3 showed that 22% of the respondents strongly agreed that they benefited from TETFund staff development programmes overseas or locally on training, seminars, conferences or workshops from their institutions, 45% agreed while 20% disagreed and 13 % strongly disagreed with the view. Item 4 showed that 20% of the respondents strongly agreed with the view that, despite TETFund intervention, there is inadequate staff development in their institutions, 56% of them agreed while 16% disagreed and 6% of them strongly disagreed with the position.

The finding indicated that Kebbi State higher institutions benefited from staff development through TETFUND normal intervention, by sponsoring of local and international training to academic staff and sponsoring local seminars and conferences or workshop to staff of Kebbi State higher institutions. This study agreed with Muhammad (2019) who revealed that TETFund intervention in staff and development led to the acquisition of higher qualifications by staff of tertiary institutions for better productivity. The study also supported the finding of Mukhtar (2020) who asserted that TETFund is actively involved in the training of academic staff in higher institutions both at home and abroad. The study agreed the finding of Nduagu & Saidu (2021) who found that staff of the institutions agreed that TETFund intervention in staff development has improved the quality of tertiary education. The study also agreed with that of Ezeali (2017) who found that TETFund intervention on human resources development to the extent to which attendance of conferences and workshops influence research and academic growth in government owned tertiary institutions in South-Eastern Nigeria.

Research Question Two

RQ2: What are the contributions of TETFund to the improvement of research and publication in higher institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020?

This research question was answered and presented in Table 3 (Appendix 1).

Table 3 (Appendix 1) showed that 55% of the respondents strongly agreed with the view that their institution benefited from research and publication through TETFUND normal interventions, 41% of them agreed while 4% disagreed and 1% of them strongly disagreed with the view. In item 2 indicated that 50% of the respondents strongly agreed that TETFund sponsors journals publication in their institutions, 49% of them agreed while 10% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed with the assertion. Item 3 showed that 33% of the respondents strongly agreed that TETFund supported research and book publication in their school, 39% agreed while 19% disagreed and 9% strongly disagreed with the position. Item 4 showed that 15% of the respondents strongly agreed with the view that TETFund contribution in the area of research and publication is effective, 55% of them agreed while 16% disagreed and 7% of them strongly disagreed with the view. Item 5 showed that 32% of the respondents strongly agreed that despite TETFund intervention, there is inadequate academic sponsorship on research in their institutions, 45% of them agreed while 16% disagreed and 7% of them strongly disagreed with the opinion.

This finding indicated that TETFund had contributed to the improvement of research and publication through normal intervention, sponsoring of journal publication, research and book publication to higher institutions in Kebbi State. The study is in line with the finding of Mukhtar (2020) who revealed that TETFund is very effective in the area of supporting and funding research and development in higher institutions in Nigeria's North-East region. The study contradicted the findings of Abdullahi (2021) who found that TETFund intervention does not have significant impact on quality and relevance to state owned tertiary institutions in North Central Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The following are the summary of findings of this study:

1. TETFUND contributed to staff improvement through normal intervention by sponsoring of local and international training to academic staff and sponsoring local seminars and conferences or workshop to academic and non-academic staff of Kebbi State higher institutions.
2. TETFund contributed to the improvement of research and publication through normal intervention by sponsoring of journal publication and research and book publication of higher institutions in Kebbi State.

Conclusions

Based on the research findings of the study. The study concluded that TETFund contributed to the sponsoring of workshops, seminars, conferences research and book publication that will aid the staff improvement of higher institutions in Kebbi State. The study conclude that the staff should acquire more skill for the improvement of higher institutions in Kebbi State. In terms of journal publication, research and book

publication should be encouraged in order to launch higher institutions on a better footing.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the conclusion drawn, the study offers the following recommendations:

1. TETFund should live up to its expectations in terms of normal intervention on staff improvement that would aid the effective improvement of higher institutions in Kebbi State. Staff should take advantage of TETFund's contribution for local and international training to acquire more skills for the improvement of higher institutions in Kebbi State.
2. Publishers should complement the effort of TETFund in assisting the Kebbi State higher institutions staff in the publication of their books and journals without payment. Such publishers should be encouraged by the State Government by granting them tax relief and other incentives for smooth operations.

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Appendix 1

Table 1. TETFund Allocation to Higher Institutions of Kebbi State from 2015-2020

S/n	Project	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
1	Physical Infrastructure/Programme Upgrade	352,000,000	1,881,000,000	1,005,000,000	660,000,000	1,022,000,000	890,280,000,000
2	Academic Staff Training & Development	330,000,000	1,000,000,000	380,000,000	970,000,000	530,000,000	666,078,802
3	Conference Attendance	90,000,000	110,000,000	98,000,000	102,000,000	150,000,000	74,000,000
4	Library Development	175,000,000	128,000,000	109,000,000	90,000,000	130,000,000	130,000,000
5	Institution Based Research	50,000,000	78,000,000	78,000,000	77,000,000	103,000,000	168,000,000
6	Manuscript Development	28,000,000.	18,000,000	16,300,000	16,000,000	20,000,000	20,000,000
7	Publication of Journal	35,000,000.	35,000,000	20,000,000	16,000,000	20,000,000	20,000,000
8	Entrepreneurship Centres	20,000,000.	20,000,000	10,000,000	21,349,200	20,000,000	
9	TETFund Project Maintenance	46,000,000.	46,000,000	35,700,000	136,000,000	60,600,000	50,000,000
10	Advocacy/ Publicity of TETFund Projects	8,000,000.00	-	-	-	-	-
11	Teaching Practice	7,000,000.00	12,000,000	20,000,000	16,308,300	22,900,000	22,900,000
12	Equipment Fabrication	10,000,000.00		6,300,000	13,628,900	10,000,000	10,900,000
13	ICT Support		50,000,000	32,500,000	20,000,000	30,000,000	45,000,000
14	Zonal Intervention			390,000,000	390,000,000	433,196,972	
	Total	1,151,000,000	3,378,000,000	2,200,800,000	2,528,286,500	2,551,696,972	891,486,878,802

Source: TETFund Website (2023).

Table 2. Contributions of TETFund to Staff Improvement in Higher Institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020

S/N	Items Statement	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Your institution benefited for staff development through TETFUND normal intervention.	262	75	87	25	1	0	0	0
2.	Did TETFund sponsor local and international training to academic staff in your institution?	192	55	149	43	9	8	0	0
3.	Did TETFund sponsor international training to non-academic staff in your institution?	15	4	45	13	168	48	122	35
4.	Have you ever benefited from TETFund staff development programmes overseas or locally on training, seminars, conferences or workshops from your institution?	76	22	157	45	71	20	46	13
5.	Despite TETFund intervention, there is inadequate staff development in your institution.	70	20	197	56	54	16	29	8

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3. Contributions of TETFund to the Improvement of Research and Publication in Higher Institutions in Kebbi State from 2015-2020?

S/N	Items Statement	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Your institution benefited from research and publication through TETFUND normal interventions.	193	55	143	41	13	4	1	0
2.	TETFund sponsors journal publication in your institution.	143	50	169	49	35	10	3	1
3.	TETFund supports research and book publication in your school.	116	33	136	39	67	19	31	9
4.	Did TETFund contribution in the area of research and publication is effective?	53	15	193	55	82	24	22	6
5.	Despite TETFund intervention, there is inadequate academic sponsorship on research in your institution.	110	32	158	45	57	16	25	7

Source: Field Survey, 2023

